

METHODS AND ALGORITHMS FOR STUDYING THE DIET OF DIFFERENTIATED DIETARY NUTRITION DURING THE PRENATAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE FETUS

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Abstract. *This article discusses mathematical models and algorithms for studying differentiated dietary nutrition. Various methods for studying dialogical nutrition have been studied. The types of deficiency or excess conditions, possible consequences for the fetus and long-term consequences are also considered.*

Key words: *mathematical modeling of nutrition, differentiated dietary nutrition, prenatal development, nutritional status disorders*

Of all the environmental factors that influence human health, the leading role belongs to nutrition[1]. At the same time, we must not forget that the younger the child is, the more attention should be paid to nutrition issues.

Scientific data from nutrigenomics indicate the impact of nutritional factors at the gene level. A successfully developing new scientific direction - epigenomics - studies the influence of various environmental factors, and above all nutrition, on the expression of genes in the mother and fetus.

Numerous studies have proven that the health of a child is greatly influenced not only by the nutrition of a pregnant and lactating woman, but also by the rational nutrition of the mother and father of the child even before conception [2]. In this regard, a new direction in the organization of nutrition for the expectant mother has emerged - "preconceptional prevention", which provides for proper nutrition of the woman before conception, which will prevent deficiency of certain nutrients during pregnancy.

Special epidemiological studies indicate that malnutrition during pregnancy can lead to serious consequences: miscarriage, premature birth, the birth of a child with various intrauterine defects, and retardation in physical and neuropsychic development. However, not only deficiency is dangerous, but also excessive consumption of some micronutrients, especially vitamin A, which is toxic in large doses.

At the same time, the deficiency of certain macro- and micronutrients in the prenatal period affects not only the formation of the fetus, but also negatively affects

the further health of the child and is a risk factor for the development of a number of diseases in adulthood.

Some types of deficiency or excess conditions, possible consequences for the fetus and long-term consequences [3]

Food Statute Violation	Fetal development disorder	Long-term consequences
Protein and energy deficiency	Intrauterine malnutrition, delayed brain development	Risk of developing diabetes mellitus, obesity, hypertension, coronary artery disease
Deficiency of polyunsaturated fatty acids	Developmental disorders of the neuroretina and brain	Vision problems, intellectual development delay
Folic acid deficiency (especially in combination with a deficiency of vitamins C, group B)	Neural tube development defects (anencephaly, spina bifida)	Neuropsychological development disorders, risk of developing cardiovascular diseases
Selenium deficiency	Weakness of labor: fetal hypoxia, iodine metabolism disorders	Selenium deficiency
Zinc deficiency	Fetal growth retardation, malnutrition, prematurity	Impaired growth, decreased immunity, impaired activity of enzyme systems
Iodine deficiency	Spontaneous abortions, stillbirths, neurodevelopmental disorders, hypothyroidism	Neurodevelopmental disorders, hypothyroidism, short stature, delayed puberty
Iron deficiency	Premature birth	Early development of anemia
Vitamin A deficiency or excess	Congenital deformities, teratogenic effects	Vitamin A deficiency or excess

Poor nutrition can lead to an imbalance between the body's needs for essential nutrients and their supply[4]. Therefore, when organizing nutrition for pregnant women, it is necessary to take into account all factors, analyze its features, taking into account the structure and traditions of nutrition[5]; physiological, biochemical and environmental factors; climatic, regional and social conditions, as well as nutrition-related diseases and the nature of professional activity.

When developing differentiated dietary nutrition during the period of prenatal development of the fetus, the following principles must be observed:

- to fortify food products, first of all, those ingredients are used, the deficiency of which actually occurs, is widespread and is not hazardous to health; for Russia these are vitamins C, group B, minerals such as iodine, iron and calcium;
- the choice of a specific functional ingredient is carried out taking into account its compatibility with the components of the food product intended for fortification, as well as its compatibility with other functional ingredients;
- functional ingredients should be added primarily to mass consumer products that are available to all groups of children's and adult nutrition and are regularly used in everyday nutrition, taking into account the recipe composition and physical state of food systems intended for enrichment;
- the introduction of a functional component into food products should not impair the consumer properties of the product, namely: reduce the content and digestibility of other nutrients;
significantly change the taste, aroma and freshness of products;
reduce product shelf life;
- preservation of the native properties, including biological activity, of additives during culinary processing and storage of the product must be ensured;
- as a result of the introduction of additives into the recipe, an improvement in the consumer quality of the product should be achieved.

In order to recognize newly developed products as functional, it is necessary to prove their usefulness, that is, to perform a biomedical assessment, the purpose of which is:

- confirm the physiological value of the product as a functional nutrition product;
- identify introduced additives with a certain biological activity, that is, determine the chemical nature;
- carry out a medical and biological assessment of culinary products for functional nutrition, in particular for harmlessness, that is, the absence of direct or collateral harmful effects, allergic effects.

In addition to medical and biological requirements, a prerequisite for the creation of functional food products is the development of recommendations for their use and, in some cases, clinical testing.

The formalized process of forming a diet and adequate nutrition regimen for a person using a traditional set of products, as well as individually manufactured products in accordance with established standards of recommended nutrition, is

presented in the form of a general dialogue algorithm (Fig. 4) and corresponds to the logic of actions of an experienced nutritionist.

Based on the characteristics of a person's condition, a parametric model of adequate nutrition is formed in the form of norms for nutrient consumption per day for a specific case. Next, the subject's existing diet is assessed based on his information about the composition of products, regime and nature of nutrition; the results of an examination of the body's condition, the amount of fat and muscle tissue, as well as the content of nutrients in the blood and tissues. If the initial diet is inadequate, its structural optimization is carried out by changing the quantitative relationships of the "more - less" type between consumed products without changing their quantity and initial composition.

Fig.-1. Algorithm of differentiated dietary nutrition during the period of prenatal development of a multistage fetus

A general algorithm has been constructed in the form of block diagrams and consists of determining the general state of pregnancy, satisfying the physiological needs of the fetus for the basic nutrients and energy necessary for its optimal growth and development.

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